

Issue with Galilean Invariance and the Emergence of the Quantum Wavelength?

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If one considers a rest mass at $x=0$, then x does not change, but time does. In other words, time and space x are decoupled and we suggest that this is a fundamental idea. If one has a frame moving with constant $-v$, then x',t' are coupled through $x'-vt'=0$ where $v=x'/t'$. We use (') to distinguish between x,t in the rest frame and the moving frame. Why should one distinguish? One may notice that $x=0$ and t , a running variable in the rest frame are decoupled while x',t' are completely coupled. Thus, there seems to be a discrepancy. If one argues that x',t' is really the same as x,t , then setting $t'=0$ means $x'=0$ which matches the rest frame situation. Setting $x'=0$, however, means $t'=0$, but t is not just 0, it may start at $t=0$ and then increase. Thus, x',t' cannot be the same as x,t which has been known since circa 1904,1905. As a result one must find a transformation between x,t and x',t' which involves v , namely the Lorentz transformation.

At this point, there has been no mention of energy or momentum. By finding a linear transformation (Lorentz transformation) from x,t to x',t' one also finds an invariant modulus. This modulus may be divided by tt' with t' written in terms of t to yield an expression which depends only on m_0 and v . In other words, x and t have disappeared and this equation may be described, upon multiplying by m_0 (m_0 =rest mass), in terms of a rest mass flux m_0v multiplied by a function of v and another function of v,m_0 . In the $v=0$ case, one has m_0 only. This then gives rise to the notion of energy and momentum for a free particle. Given the notion of an invariant of the transformation, one may create the invariant $-E't' + p'x' = -m_0c^2$.

We now go back to the central issue which led to the transformation (Lorentz transformation) in the first place. In the rest frame, x,t are decoupled while in the moving frame they are not. We suggest that the idea of decoupling is a fundamental idea, but there is nothing wrong with the coupled equation $x'-vt'$. Thus, the decoupling must be understood in a different manner. If t and x are decoupled in $-m_0c^2$, then one may suggest that there is a sense in which they are decoupled in $-Et$ and px . In the rest frame, $-m_0c^2$ has nothing to do with x , but would seem to be based on an external clock. If one considers the idea of $-m_0c^2$ as being a constant, then t is proportional to $1/m_0$. This t is now a resolution in time, i.e. a dt . In other words, it is fine to have an external clock, but there may be an internal time resolution defined which has nothing to do with the external clock. This unifies $-m_0c^2$ for different values of m_0 , each has its own resolution. It unifies in the sense of creating conservation of rest mass energy if one uses $\exp(-im_0c^2)$. In other words, this independence of x and t in the rest frame may be linked to time resolution and conservation of energy.

In the moving frame, the resolution is $1/E'$ such that $-Et$ is the same constant for frames moving with different constant $-v$ and px is also a constant suggesting a resolution in space. In this case, the resolution is $\text{constant}/p$. Furthermore, the conservation of rest mass energy now becomes conservation of energy and momentum if the t and x resolutions are independent.

Thus, we suggest that the notion of a wavelength, \hbar/p , and time period, \hbar/E , is in keeping with a fundamental idea of x,t independence in the rest frame which prevents $x'-vt'=0$, an x',t' dependent equation, from producing x',t' which matches x,t , which was the assumption for most before 1904,1905. The idea of x,t independence manifests itself not in x',t' measurements, but in resolution, it seems as well as in conservation of energy and momentum.

Different x,t Values for a Person in a Frame Moving with Constant v

We argue that a fundamental issue exists for the case of a particle with rest mass at $x=0$ viewed from a frame moving with constant $-v$. The problem is that x and t are completely decoupled (i.e. independent) in the rest frame, i.e..

Rest Frame $x=0$, t is a running variable ((1a))

Moving Frame $x'-vt'=0$ where $v=x'/t'$ ((1b))

((1b)), on the other hand, completely couples x' and t' . Thus, two very different ideas are at work. If one tries to argue that x',t' and x,t are the same (the viewpoint before 1904,, 1905), then setting $t'=0$ yields $x'=0$ which matches $x=0$. The issue is that setting $x'=0$ yields $t'=0$ and this only matches $t=0$ at one instant. Later, $x=0$, $t>0$. Thus, there is a disconnect and x',t' cannot be the same as x,t . How can one create a dependence equation: $x'-vt'=0$ ((2)) from independent x,t values? If $x=0$, then one may have a linear transformation which maps t to x' in one way and t to t' in another way such that $x'/t'=v$. This is in fact the Lorentz transformation:

$$\begin{pmatrix} g(v) & -vg(v) \\ -vg(v) & g(v) \end{pmatrix} \quad \text{where } g(v)=1/\sqrt{1-v^2/c^2} \quad ((3))$$

This leads to an invariant modulus:

$$x'x' - t't' = xx-tt \quad \text{for } c=1 \quad ((4))$$

The Notion of Energy and Momentum

At this point, no notion of energy and momentum has been mentioned. Looking at ((4)) for $x=0$, however, suggests that one may use $t' = -g t$ and divide ((4)) by $t't'$:

$$vv-1 = 1/(gg) \quad ((5))$$

The point of ((5)) is that x,t and x',t' have vanished and one only sees v which is linked with the notion of flux, e.g. mov. If one multiplies ((5)) by $momo$, then:

$$Momo \, gg \, vv - momo \, gg = momo \quad ((6))$$

Thus, ((6)) may be recast as an energy-momentum relation: $pp - EE = momo$ with $c=1$ ((7))

This means that one has two vectors (x',t') and (p',E') such that:

$-Et+px$ is an invariant.

X-t independence

We argued that x,t are independent in the rest frame, but completely dependent in the moving frame. We suggest that the idea of independence is fundamental, but does not apply to $x'-vt'=0$. How then does it apply? We suggest that it may apply to the time resolution.

For example, $-mot$ may involve using t measured from a clock which has its own time resolution. On the other hand, one might define an intrinsic resolution by $\text{constant}/m_0$. This would then unify various different m_0 values. The point is that if $\text{time resolution}=\text{constant}/m_0$ in the rest frame, then it equals $\text{constant}/E'$ in the moving frame and $p'x'$ should also represent a constant using spatial resolution i.e. $x'=\text{constant}/p'$. Thus, by introducing the idea of resolution, i.e. using $(p,-E)$ and (dx,dt) where dx and dt are resolution, one may impose independence of dx and dt , i.e. temporal and spatial resolution in both the rest frame and the moving even though $x'-vt'=0$ shows not such independence.

Conservation of Momentum and Energy

We introduced energy and momentum above through x,t and x',t' using $v=x'/t'$. Momentum and energy, however, are linked with conservation and so one may ask: How does this appear in the scheme above? We noted that in creating a time resolution for a particle at rest, one sets $-mot$ to a constant. Thus, resolution is $\text{constant}/m_0$. Different m_0 values lead to different resolutions, but we suggested that one might have the same constant for all m_0 . If t is the running variable of a periodic function, different m_0 values would lead to different periods. It is known however, that sine or cosine functions with different periods are orthogonal. Thus, if one used a two dimensional periodic function $\exp(ipx)$ and treated p before as positive and p after as negative, then $\exp(-ip_{\text{final}} x) \exp(-i p_{\text{initial}} x)$ integrates to 0 over x unless $p_{\text{final}} = p_{\text{initial}}$ and a similar argument holds for energy. Thus, the idea of $x-t$ independence in the rest frame leads to (A) the Lorentz transformation (B) the notion of energy and momentum appearing from x',t' , x,t and m_0 considerations ((C)) the notion of independent time and x resolutions and ((D)) the notion of conservation of momentum and energy conservation if one uses the resolution scheme px or $-Et$ as the arguments of complex number of unit length, i.e. $\exp(-iEt)$ or $\exp(ipx)$. In other words, in the rest frame there is no momentum, but there is still rest mass energy which must be conserved. Thus, a conservation of rest mass scheme in the rest frame, becomes generalized to conservation of momentum and energy as seen in the moving frame. If energy conservation is an independent notion in the rest frame, it remains so in the moving frame, if one forces the $-Et$ and px terms to be independent through the time and x resolution arguments.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that the very issue which causes Galilean invariance to be replaced with a Lorentz transformation, namely the independence of x, t in the rest frame, while $x' - vt' = 0$ (i.e. complete dependence) is the same reason why the quantum wavelength and period exist. At first one may think that x, t and x', t' are the same (the belief of most before 1904 1905). The problem is that $t' = 0$ means $x' = 0$ which matches $x = 0$, but $x' = 0$ means $t' = 0$ only which does not match t in the rest frame. We suggest that the independence of x, t in the rest frame is a fundamental idea which must be present in all frames, but $x' - vt' = 0$ is correct and so it must be manifested in a different way.

We start by considering the Lorentz transformation which links (x, t) to (x', t') one may create an invariant modulus $x'x' - t't' = tt$ for $x = 0$ which may be converted into an expression only containing $v = x'/t'$ and $g(v) = 1/\sqrt{1 - vv/cc}$. Multiplying by momo ($m_0 = \text{rest mass}$) one obtains an energy-momentum relation where momentum is introduced as a modified rest mass flux mv and the "other" term is called energy. This leads to the notion of two vectors (p', E') and (x', t') and the Lorentz invariant: $-Et + px$. In order to preserve the notion of x, t independence in the rest frame, one cannot use the notion of x , and t , but must rather use the idea of x and t resolution, By defining t resolution as $\text{constant}/m_0$, one has t and x resolution being independent not only in the lab frame, but in the moving frame, where $\text{constant}/E'$ is now time resolution and $\text{constant}/p'$ is spatial resolution. We also argue that the t, x resolution independence leads to conservation of momentum and energy. In the rest frame, there is no momentum, so a scheme in the rest frame linked to rest mass conservation and independent of the x portion leads to independent E and p conservation in the moving frame.